

Towards safe and sustainable by design nanomaterials: Risk and sustainability assessment on two nanomaterial case studies at early stages of development

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ABSTRACT

Nanomaterials (NNMs) have undoubtedly caused significant improvements in multiple aspects of life, with several applications in different fields, and continuous innovations to make their production and use safer for human health and the environment. Despite their evident benefits, compared to bulk components, a lot of criticism has accompanied their development and widespread application, considering their potentially harmful impacts upon release, the uncertainty regarding disposal or recycling at the end of their lifecycle, and the resource-intensive methodologies often required for their manufacture. To mitigate the risks associated with NNMs, several approaches have been proposed to estimate the health and sustainability impacts along their lifecycle, such as Risk Assessment (RA) and Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), performed either individually or integrated in a Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) approach. However, multiple differences exist in the methodology and scope of these assessments, often resulting in difficulties to combine them, or conflicting results between them. In this context, different open access tools for RA and LCA (i.e., NanoSafer, Stoffenmanager Nano, USES-LCA, openLCA), with potential applicability in SSbD, as well as a combined screening RA and LCA tool (i.e., LICARA nanoscan tool), have been examined in this paper for application in early-stage Research and Development of NNMs, with focus on two use cases: carbon NNMs (i.e., as heterogeneous catalyst supports) and metal nanoparticles (i.e., as antimicrobial coatings for surfaces). The application of tools in each case study, the significance of the functional unit definition on the outcome, and the comparison of the results achieved with each tool, are reported. Overall, this work aims to demonstrate the applicability of selected tools towards SSbD for NNMs, to bring NNM SSbD closer to practical implementation, and to support end-users.

1. Introduction

The field of nanotechnology is presenting a rapid expansion in the last decades, with nanomaterials (NNMs) being continuously developed with different elemental compositions (e.g., carbon, organic, inorganic, hybrid), dimensions (from zero-dimensional to three-dimensional), porosities (from nano to macroporous), and for different applications (e.g., medicine, agriculture, food, feed, consumer products, catalysis, energy, technology, manufacturing, etc.) [1]. The term NNMs describes materials with at least 50% (in the number-size distribution) of their constituent particles having one or more external dimensions in the size range of 1 to 100 nm. Compared to their bulk material counterparts,

NNMs offer unique properties, which can be tuned based on their size, as size-dependent effects on material properties become dominant at the nanoscale. For example, the metallic, electronic, crystalline, optical, magnetic, thermal, electrical, and mechanical properties, and their interaction with biological systems, can vary significantly depending on the NNM size, or between nano- and bulk materials of the same elemental composition [2]. These unique and highly customizable properties of NNMs have attracted significant interest, resulting in continuous development of novel NNM synthesis and customization techniques, as well as increasing application in different fields.

While the advantages and unique properties of NNMs have been reported by many researchers, several risks and disadvantages also exist.

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For example, bottom-up approaches typically employed for their production can result in significant energy and input material requirements, and subsequently high emissions of pollutants to various environmental compartments [3]. The amount and type of chemicals, as well as the manufacturing conditions, required for the synthesis of NNMs, is not only linked to negative environmental impacts, but also to risk and safety concerns for the personnel performing various tasks during manufacturing. For example, common NNM synthesis protocols include the use of toxic, flammable, corrosive or explosive substances, operating at high temperatures and pressures, thus requiring specialized personnel that participates in frequent hazard trainings, as well as highly controlled workspace with integrated safety measures, to minimize the risk of potential accidents [4]. The environmental and health risks associated with NNMs are not limited to the energy, raw material inputs and working conditions, but, to a large extent, stem from the properties of NNMs themselves. For instance, several reports have highlighted the health concerns associated with exposure to NNMs via inhalation, oral or dermal exposure [5]. Furthermore, in addition to human health risks, exposure to NNMs in the environment has been linked to ecotoxicity in different environmental compartments (e.g., freshwater, marine water, soil) [6–8].

Several methodologies can be used to assess the risks and impacts of NNMs, such as Risk Assessment (RA) and Life Cycle Assessment (LCA). Briefly, chemical RA methodologies, as stipulated in Council Directive 98/24/EC [9], involve the identification of hazards and exposure potential of a certain group (e.g., workers, human populations, or the environment) to a certain material (e.g., a chemical), as well as an estimation of a dose-response upon exposure (e.g., via *in-vivo*, *in-vitro* or *in-silico* methods). Based on these, risk characterization can be performed for the specific material and target group, and uncertainties can be estimated. The outcomes of RA can be used to propose risk management procedures or measures, and to help guide decision making for material development [10]. LCA is an international, standardized (ISO 14040, ISO 14044, [11,12]) and holistic methodology to quantify the potential environmental impacts, such as climate change, resource depletion, ecotoxicity and human toxicity, of a process or a product, by inventorying all flows from and to the system boundaries along its lifecycle (e.g., emissions, resources), and calculating their corresponding potential environmental impacts (e.g., climate change or resource depletion potential). LCA methodology can be used to guide decision making, compare process or product alternatives in terms of environmental impacts, identify problem-shifting between life stages when comparing alternatives, and highlight hotspots that contribute most towards the impacts, which can thereafter be prioritized for mitigation actions.

NNMs present a challenge for both RA and LCA. For example, NNMs with the same chemical composition can have different physicochemical properties, which in turn affect their risk and environmental impacts. A case-by-case evaluation of different NNMs would therefore be required to properly estimate their specific risks and impacts, which is not practical, given the large number of different formulations that have been developed. Furthermore, testing NNM toxicity on a case-by-case basis would require a lot of experimental animals, effort, and economic resources to carry out. Instead, different approaches have been proposed, such as the application of (Quantitative) Structure Activity Relationships, grouping methods, read-across and high-throughput screening, to eliminate the need for individual assessment of different NNMs [13]. From an LCA perspective, challenges related to NNMs have been identified in terms of selecting an appropriate functional unit, collecting sufficient inventory data, and evaluating their impacts with the currently available methodologies [3]. Specifically, the functional unit in LCA needs to quantitatively and qualitatively reflect all aspects related to the function of the product under investigation. Given the wide variety of possible applications, selecting a proper functional unit, as well as a reference product to compare NNMs in terms of function, can be challenging. Collection of inventory data, particularly for novel

processes such as the ones involved in NNM Research and Development (R&D), can be difficult, as technology developers may not provide access to information due to commercial confidentiality. Finally, as is the case for RA, an accurate estimation of the environmental impacts and endpoint indicators is challenging, as information regarding the biological effects and fate of NNMs is generally lacking.

Aside from the individual challenges of RA and LCA in NNM assessments, several constraints have been reported when the two methods are combined, either as an integrated methodology, or by combining the results of individual assessments. RA and LCA approach environmental issues from different perspectives, and can therefore provide complementary information, as well as conflicting results [14]. For example, RA on a NNM-containing product may reveal higher risk compared to a product without NNMs, due to the risk of NNM release during certain process steps, whereas an LCA on the same NNM-based product may reveal an overall benefit, due to altered properties of the product containing NNMs (e.g., longer lifetime, less frequent or resource-intensive cleaning or repairs needed along its lifecycle). Despite the difficulties to bridge the gap between RA and LCA, it is widely recognized that a combined approach is necessary towards Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) development of NNMs. SSbD is a pre-market approach to incorporate safety and sustainability criteria in the design of new products at early stages of development. SSbD goes beyond simply adding sustainability considerations, for example in the form of LCA, on top of Safe by Design methodologies (i.e., methods that incorporate RA in the early stages of development); instead, it attempts to interlink safety and sustainability from a systems' perspective [15]. Safety and Sustainability criteria during early stages of development allow to steer scientific effort towards the most promising candidates in terms of risks and impacts, and to guide the development of new NNMs from a lifecycle perspective, focusing on formulations that can be easily managed at the end of their lifecycle [14].

Considering the need for an integrated, standardized approach towards Safety and Sustainability assessment, the European Commission (EC) and Joint Research Centre (JRC) have developed the SSbD framework, aiming to steer the innovation process towards the green and sustainable industrial transition, to substitute or minimize the production and use of substances of concern, and to minimize the impacts on health, climate and the environment along the entire lifecycle of chemicals, materials and products [16–21]. The SSbD framework is represented schematically in Fig. 1. Briefly, the framework consists of two phases: the (Re-)Design phase and the Assessment phase, which are performed iteratively along the innovation process, i.e., at every stage of the development of new materials (ideation stage, lab-scale development stage, pilot scale development stage, etc.). In the (Re-)Design phase, SSbD practitioners can set (Re-)Design Principles (Step D1), apply (Re-)Design Actions (Step D2) and evaluate them with (Re-)Design Indicators (Step D3) during the material development process. At the end of each stage along the innovation process, the (Re-)Design phase is followed by the Assessment phase, wherein the five assessment steps of the SSbD framework are applied (Steps A1–A5). Each of these steps includes criteria for the evaluation of the developed material, resulting in a calculated Score for each step, while Steps related to Risk and Safety (Steps A1–A3) also include cut-off points, which determine whether a material can proceed to the next step, or sent back to the (Re-)Design phase. Importantly, the functionality of the material is taken into account for the sustainability assessment, wherein material alternatives are compared in terms of their function for a specific application, and no cut-off points are set of the SSbD score for Steps A4 and A5. Based on the overall SSbD score (by combining individual scores from each step), and insights gained via the SSbD assessment on the hotspots for safety and sustainability impacts, material developers can adapt the material production process in the Re-Design phase in an iterative manner, in order to further improve the SSbD score of the material, before selecting the final process, which can thereafter be upscaled and proceed to the next stage of the innovation process.

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of SSbD framework.

For each step of the Assessment phase, JRC has proposed several tools and databases that can be used for assessment, including both open-access and paid options [18,20]. In addition, significant research efforts have been made to demonstrate and promote the applicability of the SSbD methodology, and to develop repositories of tools, databases and recommendations for the application of the SSbD framework [22–33]. Notably, in order to facilitate the implementation of SSbD, the EC-funded PARC project (Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals) has recently developed a comprehensive toolbox for each step of the SSbD assessment and each stage of the innovation process [34]. While the toolbox developed by PARC is not specifically aimed towards assessment of NNMs, several nano-specific approaches have also been proposed for individual [35–38] and combined Risk and Sustainability assessment [39–42], as well as integrated SSbD approaches for NNMs [15,43–49].

The aim of the present study is to investigate the applicability of some open-access RA and LCA tools and databases, currently not all included in the PARC toolbox, both specific and non-specific to NNM, for different steps of SSbD assessment on NNMs. Specifically, the individual assessment tools selected were openLCA (representing an LCA tool suitable for Step A4 of SSbD), USES-LCA (able to generate characterization factors, fate, exposure and damage factors for multiple substances, for both human health and the environment, and therefore suitable for calculating characterization factors for LCA in Step A4, as well as risk assessment of materials in Step A3), NanoSafer and Stoffenmanager Nano tools (both suitable for occupational exposure and RA in Steps A2 and A3 of SSbD). A simple integrated tool for safety and

sustainability assessment was also examined (LICARA nanoscan tool), and the results were compared to dedicated tools for individual RA and LCA assessments. Tools were selected and evaluated based on several criteria: the objective and type of outcomes in relation to different SSbD assessment steps (i.e., including workplace exposure), price and availability (with focus on open-access tools), required expertise, availability of characterization data needed as input, and decision-making guidance (i.e., whether they can easily be used to select between process alternatives).

The tools were applied in two laboratory scale protocols for NNM synthesis: carbon NNMs (i.e., as heterogeneous catalyst supports) and metal nanoparticles (NNPs) (i.e., as antimicrobial materials for surface disinfection). In each case study, a variation was considered in the NNM synthesis protocol, namely two different acids for the oxidation of carbon NNMs, and two different elemental compositions of metal NNPs, to investigate whether the applied tools are suitable to distinguish between the two alternative products. To compare the RA and LCA tools in terms of decision-making guidance between alternatives (i.e., whether the same product between the two alternatives is better from both a sustainability and safety perspective), every assessment needs to be performed on the same basis (i.e., functional unit). Here, the functional unit was defined for each use case considering the envisioned application and functionality of NNMs, namely the catalytically active surface area of a metal nano-catalyst upon impregnation on the carbon NNMs, as a result of the different amount of anchoring sites on the two NNMs treated with a different acid, and the antimicrobial properties of metal NNPs, as a result of the different NNP sizes and elemental composition.

Importantly, the functional unit based on a selected application serves as basis for comparison among NNM alternatives not only for LCA, but also for RA tools, to highlight the importance of a functionality-based assessment in all steps of the SSbD Assessment phase. The study aims (a) to determine whether the selected tools are suitable for SSbD assessment of NNMs; (b) to determine whether a simple, integrated tool could be a suitable screening method for early-stage NNM development, by comparing its outcomes with more specialized, individual assessment tools; and (c) to investigate the impact of the functional unit definition on both LCA and RA methodologies, as this is often omitted in the latter. The outcomes achieved with each tool were compared, to demonstrate the similarities and differences between the safety and sustainability aspects of the investigated NNMs, and to reflect upon the potential applicability of the selected tools for a complete NNM SSbD assessment.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Description of the selected tools for RA and LCA

The openLCA software, developed by GreenDelta, was used to perform the LCA for the two case studies. The software can be downloaded for free from the internet (<https://www.openlca.org/>) [50] and does not require installation. Several libraries of materials, processes and impact assessment methods are compatible with openLCA and can be downloaded for free from the openLCA Nexus website (<https://nexus.openlca.org/>) [51], whereas many more libraries and methods are also available to purchase. In order to install the libraries and perform the analysis, the instructions were followed as shown in the free videos available in the openLCA website (<https://www.openlca.org/learning/>) [52]. Assessment using the openLCA software was performed using the corresponding LCA ISOs [11,12]. The impact assessment was performed using the Environmental Footprint (EF) mid-point indicator method.

The USES-LCA 3.0, based on Simplebox 3.0 [53] EUSES [54] and USES-LCA [55], is an excel-based tool that can be used to calculate midpoint and endpoint characterization factors for ecotoxicity and human toxicity, fate, exposure, and intake factors, as well as effect and damage factors, for a variety of chemical substances (over 3000 in the current version). The most recent version of the tool was kindly provided by van Zelm and co-workers [56,57].

The Stoffenmanager Nano module (version 1.0.10) is an online tool for the qualitative assessment of occupational health risks from inhalation exposure to manufactured nanoobjects. The tool can be accessed from its website (<https://nano.stoffenmanager.com/>) [58], after creation of a free account in the Stoffenmanager® knowledge-based platform (<https://stoffenmanager.com/>) [59]. In addition to the nano-specific tool, the Stoffenmanager® knowledge-based platform offers services aimed at reducing exposure risks to hazardous substances and biological agents in the workplace. Practitioners can create up to 35 products and perform up to 35 RAs with a free account, whereas multiple licensing options exist for a paid account.

The combined control banding and risk management tool for NNMs, NanoSafer v2, was selected to investigate the exposure risk and recommended control associated with the production and handling of engineered NNMs. This tool was developed by the National Research Centre for the Working Environment, Copenhagen, and the Danish Technological Institute, Høje Taastrup. It was further revised in collaboration with the Danish Nanosafety Centre and the Danish government, and applied in European research projects. The tool is available to use for free after registration on the website (<http://www.nanosafer.org/>) [60].

Finally, an integrated methodology for RA and LCA, as well as economic and social criteria, has been developed in the context of the European-funded project LICARA (Grant Agreement 315494) [61]. The LICARA nanoSCAN tool v3.0 was accessed for free after creating an account on the website (<https://diamonds.tno.nl/licara/>) [62].

2.2. Description of case studies

Two NNM synthesis case studies were analyzed in this work, to demonstrate the applicability of the selected RA, LCA and integrated tools. Specifically, the synthesis of carbon nanofibers (CNFs) via Chemical Vapour Deposition (CVD), as described by Bitter and co-workers [63–65], and the synthesis of metal NNPs with different elemental composition via electric arc evaporation, as described by Slotte and co-workers [66,67], were considered. Variations were tested in both case studies in the NNM preparation protocol, in order to investigate if the selected tools are suitable to provide decision support for alternative processes. Specifically, for CNF synthesis, two different acids were modelled for the reflux treatment of the produced NNMs, namely nitric acid (HNO₃) and hydrochloric acid (HCl). Both acids serve to remove the nickel catalyst from the synthesized NNMs, whereas nitric acid also serves to introduce oxygen groups (O-groups) on the surface of the CNFs [68]. Consequently, the choice of acid determines the anchoring and resulting average size of metal NNPs on the CNF upon impregnation [69,70]. To reflect the difference of the resulting material in the LCA analysis, the functional unit was equalized in terms of metal surface area, after impregnation with the same metal loading, as shown in Table 1. The system boundaries are shown in Fig. 2.

For the second case study, the variation of elemental composition of metal NNPs was examined, specifically by investigating Silver (Ag) and Copper (Cu) NNPs. Given the envisioned utilization of the NNPs as an antimicrobial coating for surfaces, the two elemental compositions were selected based on the different antimicrobial activity [71], due to the different metal and different NNP sizes produced with electric arc evaporation [66]. The reference flow for LCA analysis was defined based on different amount of NNPs needed to offer the same antimicrobial functionality. In order to define the functional unit in terms of antimicrobial activity, considering the elemental composition and NNP size, the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) values reported by Asghar and co-workers [72] were used, which correspond to 8 µg/ml for Ag NNPs (spherical, 10–20 nm), and 32 µg/ml for Cu NNPs (spherical, 26–40 nm). While the average size of Cu NNPs prepared via electric arc evaporation (58 nm) is larger than the size range reported in antimicrobial activity assays, it was assumed that the MIC is the same for the two types of Cu NNPs, as the objective of this paper is to demonstrate the applicability of the selected RA and LCA tools, and not to provide a detailed assessment of metal NNPs. A more accurate antimicrobial activity measurement should be performed by RA and LCA practitioners for a precise assessment. Given that Cu NNPs have 4 times higher MIC than Ag NNPs, a functional unit and reference flow were selected, as shown in Table 1. The system boundaries are shown in Fig. 3.

A schematic of the two case studies and the applied tools for assessment is shown in Fig. 4.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Risk assessment of NNM manufacture with NanoSafer tool

In order to estimate the nano-specific hazards and recommended risk management protocols for the manufacture of NNMs in the two case studies, the NanoSafer tool was used. In the case of CNFs, the following

Table 1
Functional Unit and Reference flow for the two selected case studies.

Case Study	Functional Unit	Reference Flow
CNF as metal catalyst support	CNF mass that can support metal NNPs of 1.75 m ² surface area	0.7 grams of CNFs refluxed with HNO ₃ , or 2.5 grams of CNFs refluxed with HCl
Metal NNPs as antimicrobial coatings	Inhibition of microbial growth in 125 Liters of microbial broth	1 gram of Ag NNPs, or 4 grams of Cu NNPs

Fig. 2. Value chain and System Boundaries of CNF synthesis via chemical vapour deposition (CVD).

Fig. 3. Value chain and System Boundaries of Ag or Cu metal NNPs synthesis via electric arc evaporation.

materials were examined with the model: Fumed Silica powder, Nickel-Silica catalyst (before calcination) of the desired dimensions after sieving, Nickel-Silica catalyst (before calcination) with smaller than the desired dimensions after sieving, CNFs with surface functionalization (i. e., assuming O-groups are introduced on the surface after HNO_3

treatment), and CNFs without surface functionalization (i.e., assuming no O-groups are introduced on the surface after HCl treatment). For the second case study (antimicrobial Ag and Cu NNPs), two materials were modelled: Ag NNPs with 16 nm particle size, and Cu NNPs with 58 nm particle size. An estimation of the respirable dustiness index could not be performed, and therefore the highest value was selected from the drop-down menu, as was suggested in the tool for new materials with no known value. No hazard statements could be retrieved for the Nickel-Silica catalyst, and therefore the hazard statements of Fumed Silica and Nickel Nitrate were added as a proxy. Some bibliographical sources were used to estimate the input parameters for modelling these materials with the NanoSafer tool. It would be advisable, however, that practitioners perform a more careful selection of proxy compounds to get a more representative value for these parameters, or, ideally, perform characterizations of the investigated NNMs, such as microscopy and physisorption measurements, in order to use accurate values for the materials under investigation. An overview of the input parameters and sources of additional information are shown in Supplementary Information (SI, Section S1, Table S1). In addition to the materials, processes were also modelled in the NanoSafer tool, wherein these materials are used during the manufacture of CNFs and metal NNPs. Specifically, in

Fig. 4. Schematic representation of case studies and tested tools in the present manuscript.

the case of CNFs, the following processes were modelled: weighing fumed silica to be added in the reactor for catalyst growth, grinding and sieving the nickel-silica catalyst, and grinding and sieving the produced CNFs. In the case of metal NNPs, the process of harvesting the synthesized NNPs from the filter was modelled. The parameters used to describe these processes are shown in SI (Section S1, Table S2). The assessment for different compounds and operations was performed, and the results are shown in SI (Section S1, Figs S1-S2 for silica and nickel-silica) and Figs. 5 – 8 (for metal NNPs and CNFs).

The NanoSafer tool generates an estimation of the near-field and far-field exposure potential, and can further differentiate between the acute and daily exposure potential. An exposure potential score between 0 and ∞ for each of the four exposure categories is calculated by the tool, with values above 1 indicating critical exposure potential, and values equal to or above 0.1 requiring exposure management actions. A hazard level score between 0.2 and 1.0 is also estimated based on the properties of NNMs and processing conditions selected by the practitioner, wherein score equal to 1.0 is assigned to materials with high potential hazard. Finally, the tool generates recommendations for protective equipment that should be used during the described operations, to minimize the health risks to the practitioners. Considering the two case studies investigated here, the results reveal the suitability of the NanoSafer tool to help guide the selection between process alternatives. For example, in the case of metal NNPs, the results of the NanoSafer tool clearly demonstrate a lower hazard level for Ag NNPs (Fig. 5), compared to Cu NNPs (Fig. 6). The difference is partially explained by the reference flow definition, as a lower mass of Ag NNPs (1 gram) compared to Cu NNPs (4 grams) is considered. However, even when comparing the same amount of Cu and Ag NNPs (1 gram), a better score in terms of hazard level (0.26 compared to 0.67625) and daily exposure potential (“low” compared to “intermediate”) is calculated for Ag NNPs, compared to Cu NNPs (results not shown). These findings indicate that NanoSafer is a suitable RA tool to investigate and help guide the selection among process alternatives for the case study of metal NNPs.

In the case of CNFs, a higher exposure potential can be observed for HCl-washed (Fig. 7), compared to HNO₃-washed CNFs (Fig. 8), considering all four exposure categories (i.e., near-field and far-field acute and daily exposure potential), while both materials were scored with the highest estimated hazard level (equal to 1) within the range of the tool (0.2 – 1.0). Therefore, from an RA perspective, using HNO₃ results in lower risks during manufacture. It should be noted that the difference between the two acids in terms of exposure potential is the result of the reference flow definition, whereas comparing the same amount of CNFs undergoing sieving for the same duration resulted in identical results with the NanoSafer tool (not shown). A more careful definition of the reference flow would be required by the practitioners, based on experimental data, to accurately describe the functionality and resulting CNF properties. For example, in the context of this research, the only difference considered between the HCl- and HNO₃-washed CNFs was the surface O-groups introduced in the second case, which would result in different metal NNP size upon impregnation. However, different acids used for the pre-treatment of carbonaceous supports can also result in different structural integrity and product yield. For example, it has been previously shown that Activated Carbon (AC) NNMs, refluxed with different concentrations of HNO₃, exhibit increasing mass loss after the reflux process with increasing concentration of HNO₃, indicating that the highly concentrated HNO₃ leads to disintegration of the carbonaceous material [73]. The surface area and total pore volume of AC has also been shown to decrease with increasing concentration of HNO₃ during the reflux treatment, likely due to the collapse of the pore walls at high HNO₃ concentration [73]. While the effects of HNO₃ concentration depend on the exact type of carbonaceous NNM examined [73], it is reasonable to assume that similar effects may be present for the CNFs investigated here, for which a reflux process in concentrated (68%) nitric acid and diluted (1M) hydrochloric acid was considered. The resulting properties of the CNF samples, which can affect their

functionality as catalyst supports, ought to be reflected in the reference flow, which can in turn alter the results of the RA.

3.2. Inhalation risk assessment of NNM with Stoffenmanager Nano

The Stoffenmanager Nano module was selected as an alternative RA tool for the evaluation of the investigated NNMs, as well as a mandatory step in the combined LCA-RA methodology for the LICARA tool (see Section 3.4). Metal NNPs and CNFs were modelled according to the information shown in SI (Section S2, Table S3). For metal NNPs, two assessments were performed, to evaluate the inhalation risk during the synthesis/harvesting of NNPs from the filter, as well as the risk during the application of NNPs on a surface as an antimicrobial coating. For CNFs, two assessments were performed, to estimate the inhalation risk from handling CNF agglomerates during crushing and sieving of the manufactured CNFs, and during weighing of metal-impregnated CNFs to add as catalyst in the reaction medium (i.e., use phase). It is possible that some CNFs are released during the CVD step. However, given that the toxic gas carbon monoxide is used for synthesis, it is reasonably assumed that this process is carried out in a closed ventilated cabinet, and that practitioners are not in contact with the CNF-containing exhaust gas. The tool generates a Hazard Class Score (A-E), an Exposure Class score (1-4), and a Risk Priority Score (III-I), which are also shown in Table S3 of the SI for the characterized NNMs. It should be noted that some information used for modelling each NNM was selected based on an educated guess, particularly related to the working conditions (e.g., ventilation, type of mask used for protection during manufacture, etc.), since this information is specific to the protocols applied by each manufacturer and could not be retrieved online. Nevertheless, practitioners using this tool are reasonably assumed to be aware of this information related to their own manufacturing processes, and should be able to accurately describe the working conditions when applying this tool.

Based on the results of the RA with the Stoffenmanager Nano module, it is evident that it can help guide practitioners in deciding among process alternatives, considering that different RA scores were calculated between process alternatives (i.e., between Cu and Ag NNPs, and between HNO₃- and HCl-treated CNFs). A similar trend can be observed between the two tested RA tools, wherein Cu NNPs result in higher risk compared to Ag NNPs (Figs. 5, 6, Table S3), and HNO₃-treated CNFs result in lower risk than HCl-treated CNFs (Figs. 7, 8, Table S3). As was also discussed in Section 3.1 related to the NanoSafer tool results, the difference between the two CNF protocols could only be reflected in terms of reference flow (i.e., different amount of yearly production of CNFs, and therefore different duration of CNF grinding and sieving). Practitioners are advised to perform some basic characterization of the materials they intend to compare, to better reflect the possible differences that result from protocol alternatives. For example, disintegration of CNFs after reflux in concentrated HNO₃ may result in different size of nanofibers, which will likely change the RA calculation with this tool. Nevertheless, the results shown in Table S3 (for the Stoffenmanager Nano tool), Figs. 5 - 8 and Fig. S1 – Fig. S2 (for the NanoSafer tool) confirm the suitability of both selected RA tools to provide a quick assessment of risks for the two use cases examined here. Furthermore, the results presented here confirm the suitability of the selected nano-specific RA tools for application in Step A2 of SSbD assessment, related to inhalation risks. Namely, the selected tools allow the input by the user of hazard properties, the description and estimation of exposure scenarios for precursors, final products and processes during different steps in the manufacture of NNMs under assessment, the description of protective equipment utilized during production, and the calculation of quantitative metrics such as Risk Characterization scores for human health, which can be used as criteria required for Step A2 assessment of the SSbD framework [18,20].

Fig. 5. Results of RA with NanoSafer tool for the process of harvesting 1 gram of Ag NNPs.

Fig. 6. Results of RA with NanoSafer tool for the process of harvesting 4 grams of Cu NNPs.

Fig. 7. Results of RA with NanoSafer tool for the process of grinding and sieving 2.5 grams of HCl-washed CNFs.

Fig. 8. Results of RA with NanoSafer tool for the process of grinding and sieving 0.7 grams of HNO₃-washed CNFs.

3.3. Sustainability assessment of NNMs along their lifecycle with openLCA and USES-LCA

The laboratory-scale manufacture of NNMs for the two investigated use cases was examined with the openLCA software, and the results are shown in Figs. 9 – 10. Some precursors were not available in the free databases of openLCA, and therefore proxies had to be utilized. Specifically, nickel nitrate was modelled as nickel sulfate, and the required input amount was calculated based on the molecular weight of the two metal salts. Carbon monoxide was not available, and therefore a process had to be created for the production of this gas. Specifically, a thermochemical CO₂ splitting process was modelled, as has been previously described [74], assuming a 10% conversion of CO₂ to CO, and an

estimation of the energy requirement based on the reported activation energy of 46.6 kJ/mol.

For both case studies, the LCA results reveal that one alternative clearly outperforms the other in most impact categories. In the case of CNFs, the superior sustainability of HNO₃-washed, compared to HCl-washed CNFs (Fig. 9), is due to the definition of the reference flow, which corresponds to 2.5 grams of HCl- and 0.7 grams of HNO₃-washed CNFs. In fact, when the two products are compared on an equal mass basis, the HCl-treated CNFs result in lower environmental impacts for all impact categories, corresponding, for example, to 3.1% lower climate change potential and 19% lower freshwater ecotoxicity potential (not shown). These differences are due to the different acids used, as well as the different concentration of acid, wherein HNO₃ was modelled as 68%

Fig. 9. Life Cycle Impact Assessment of CNF manufacture process with HCl and HNO₃ acids for the reflux oxidation. Results are expressed per reference flow, which corresponds to 0.7 grams for HNO₃-treated CNF and 2.5 grams for HCl-treated CNF.

Fig. 10. Life Cycle Impact Assessment of Ag and Cu metal NNP manufacture process. Results are expressed per reference flow, which corresponds to 1 gram for Ag and 4 grams for Cu NNPs.

concentrated (i.e., 16.24M), whereas HCl was modelled as 1M acid solution. For metal NNPs, Cu resulted in lower environmental impacts than Ag in most impact categories when compared based on the defined reference flows (i.e., 4 grams of Cu compared to 1 gram of Ag, Fig. 10). Cu also resulted in much lower environmental impacts than Ag in all impact categories when compared on an equal mass basis, with nearly 95% lower climate change potential and 59% lower freshwater ecotoxicity potential (not shown). These differences are due to the higher amount of electricity required for electric arc evaporation of Ag (2220 MJ) compared to Cu (501 MJ and 4.2 MJ for vacuum melting pre-treatment of the Cu wire), to produce the same amount of metal NNPs (1 kg), as well as the higher amount of N₂ gas required for 1 kg Ag NNPs (577 kg) than for Cu NNPs (111 kg) [66]. Furthermore, the starting

material (i.e., Ag or Cu wire anode) also plays a significant role in the environmental impact of each product alternative, with the production of 1 kg Cu wire corresponding to lower impacts in all categories than the production of 1 kg Ag wire, for example 98.5% lower climate change potential, 58% lower freshwater ecotoxicity potential, and 94% lower mineral and metal resource depletion potential.

Recently, the impact category of resource depletion for different metals has received attention by LCA practitioners, who have proposed that a distinction ought to be made between short and long-term depletion of metals incorporated into products, wastes, or released as emissions. For example, depletion of metals from sources that are not considered mineral resources within the time frame of the study, metals that are incorporated in products or wastes (that are not currently

receiving treatment for recovery, but may serve as source for the recovery of metals in the future), and metals lost as emissions that may in the future form a new source of extraction, should be differentiated from truly dissipative emissions, i.e., emissions that result in present and future loss of accessibility to the resource in question [75,76]. To that end, methodologies and indicators have been proposed to estimate and incorporate into LCA the true dissipative losses of metals [75,77,78], with, for example, Ag exhibiting higher dissipation [75,78], and marginally lower lifecycle [79], compared to Cu. Insights from this type of analysis can be used to generate both midpoint and endpoint indicators [78,80], which can be used to improve the current method of calculating minerals' and metals' resource depletion impacts in Life Cycle Impact Assessment methodologies. In the case study examined here on metal NNP, the results on resource depletion (Fig. 10) are in agreement with the findings on comparative metal dissipation rates from literature. Such metrics, aiming to provide a more realistic sustainability assessment of resources, ought to be incorporated both in individual LCA assessments, as well as in integrated SSbD methodology guidelines, particularly in the context of metal NNMs, whose waste collection and recovery efficiency via recycling may be substantially different compared to their bulk metal counterparts.

Aside from the comparison between process alternatives, LCA also allows the identification of hotspots, i.e., steps or flows that have a high contribution to the environmental impact, and thus allows practitioners to target hotspots when re-designing a certain process, to decrease the overall environmental impact. For example, in the case of HNO₃-treated CNF synthesis, for all impact categories examined, the highest contribution was due to the CNF growth process via CVD. Within the CVD process, the main contributor was the electricity consumption, which corresponded to, for example, 86% of the total climate change potential, and 70% of the freshwater ecotoxicity potential. Significant contribution to the impacts of CVD can also be attributed to the nickel-silica catalyst (10% and 11% contribution to these impact categories) and carbon monoxide input (4% and 19% contribution to these impact categories). In the case of metal NNPs, both the electricity consumption and the metal anode had significant contributions to the total impact, depending on the metal. For example, for Cu, climate change potential was mainly due to electricity consumption (53%), whereas for Ag it was mainly due to the input metal requirement (81%). Based on such insights, practitioners may consider adaptations to their manufacturing process during the SSbD (Re-)Design phase, such as use of renewable electricity for energy-intensive process steps, or selection of a different carbon source and catalyst for CVD. Adaptations may also be tailored to specific product alternatives; for example, a switch to renewable electricity may be more beneficial for Cu NNPs, whereas it may have only a small contribution to the sustainability of Ag NNPs, and could be considered redundant for Ag, particularly if it requires costly installations of new equipment in order to be implemented.

The LCA results shown in Figs. 9–10 do not include NNM emissions from the manufacturing process. In an attempt to estimate the environmental impact of NNM emissions, different strategies can be used, such as calculating the dispersion using specialized modelling tools (e.g., the SimpleBox4.0-nano tool, [35]), or measuring the weight of input and output material during different process steps, to calculate the amount that escapes to the environment (e.g., via ventilation or via cleaning laboratory surfaces with water, which is eventually discarded via wastewater treatment). A careful estimation would be particularly important for the case of CNFs examined here, considering that disintegration of HNO₃-washed CNFs could result in higher material losses in the form of small-size particulate matter, compared to HCl-washed CNF, and this could result in differences between the two NNM alternatives in terms of environmental impact. Nevertheless, detailed information regarding the structural integrity of CNFs, type of ventilation, and manner of cleaning laboratory surfaces, was not available for the two use cases examined here. Therefore, for simplicity, release of NNMs was assumed to correspond to 10% of the weight, for both alternatives in

both case studies.

For metal NNP releases during manufacture, a certain amount of metal NNPs may escape from the collection filter and be vented outside the manufacturing room together with the used N₂ gas. Assuming that the manufacturing facility is set in an urban environment, the characterization factors for emissions to urban air were calculated with the USES-LCA tool, and are shown in SI (Section S3, Table S4). Given that nano-specific impacts cannot be calculated with USES-LCA, the emissions of metal NNPs were estimated as metal emissions. When emissions to urban air are compared on an equal mass basis, the characterization factors (i.e., the amount of kg 1,4-DCB equivalents per kg of metal emission) are higher for Ag than Cu in every category (i.e., every environmental compartment for which the toxicity is estimated), thus indicating the higher toxicity potential of Ag, compared to Cu. When the amounts of metal are corrected considering the reference flows (i.e., 4 times more Cu than Ag, in grams), the freshwater ecotoxicity potential is 24% higher for Cu, whereas the soil ecotoxicity potential is 29% higher for Ag, and for other impact categories it is over 96% higher for Ag, compared to Cu. Therefore, it is evident that for most impact categories, Ag emissions during the manufacturing phase have a higher environmental impact than Cu. For CNFs, the emission flow “particles, PM10” (i.e., particulate matter with diameter of 10 μm or less) to the compartment “urban air, close to ground” was used to simulate the emissions from the manufacturing process. No difference was assumed in terms of size between HCl- and HNO₃-washed CNFs, and no specification could be modelled with openLCA in terms of toxicity as a result of CNF surface properties (i.e., potentially different toxicity due to the O-groups present on the surface of HNO₃-treated CNFs). Therefore, the same result was calculated for both product alternatives, which corresponds to the impact category “particulate matter” with an impact of 0.55•10⁻⁴ disease inc. per kg of emitted particles. This impact category in the EF Impact Assessment method is aimed to quantify the damage to human health and change in mortality due to outdoor and indoor emissions of particulate matter in urban and rural areas, expressed as deaths per kg PM2.5 equivalents in previous versions of the EF method, and as Disease Incidences per kg PM in the current method [81]. Considering the selected reference flows, a higher impact corresponds to 2.5 grams of HCl-washed CNFs, compared to 0.7 grams of HNO₃-washed CNFs, assuming 10% emission for each product during manufacture. It is expected, however, that the suspected disintegration of CNFs after reflux in concentrated HNO₃ may result in smaller particles being released than what was assumed here (PM10), which also correspond to higher impacts in the particulate matter impact category (i.e., 4.3 times higher for particles with size PM2.5-10). Therefore, practitioners are advised to perform a good characterization of NNM alternatives, in order to achieve more accurate prediction of the comparative environmental impacts.

In addition to the manufacturing phase, LCA can be used to evaluate the environmental impacts of NNMs at the end of their lifecycle, and to compare different treatment processes, such as recycling, landfilling, and wastewater treatment. For metal NNPs, as nano-specific impact calculations cannot be performed with openLCA and USES-LCA, the impacts associated with wastewater treatment and landfilling were estimated for the corresponding metal emission. In Table S4, the characterization factors for Ag (I) and Cu (II) toxicity potential for different environmental compartments is shown, as calculated with USES-LCA, when metals are released to a sewage treatment plan or to industrial soil. Industrial soil was selected as an environmental compartment to simulate landfilling of metal NNPs, assuming, for example, that metals ions can be released to the soil via leaching upon landfilling. On an equal mass basis, Ag has higher toxicity potential in all impact categories examined, whereas when the reference flow is considered (1 gram Ag, 4 grams Cu), the freshwater ecotoxicity potential is higher for Cu (by 28% for wastewater treatment and 25% for landfilling), while Ag results in higher soil ecotoxicity potential (by 45% for wastewater treatment and 28% for landfilling), and in significantly higher potential in the

remaining impact categories (i.e., over 95% for both wastewater treatment and landfilling). The impacts of landfilling and metal NNP recycling were also estimated with openLCA, and the results are shown in SI (Section S3, Fig. S3). Results here are calculated per impact category, wherein the metal with the highest impact is set to 100%, and the impact of the other metal is expressed as a percentage compared to the highest impact. The same landfilling process from the LCA library was selected for both metals, and therefore the calculated impacts are mainly due to the reference flow definition, leading to four times higher impacts for Cu than Ag for most impact categories, except for freshwater ecotoxicity and non-cancer human toxicity. The difference for these impact categories is due to the modelled metal emission to soil (i.e., assuming leaching of metal upon landfilling), which has a much higher impact for Ag than for Cu on an equal mass basis. Instead, for recycling, metal-specific processes were selected from the LCA library, resulting in much lower impacts for Cu than Ag in most impact categories, despite the four times lower mass of Ag, compared to Cu. Based on these results, assuming that metal NNPs are recycled at the end of their lifecycle, Cu is shown to be a more sustainable alternative than Ag, even considering its lower antimicrobial activity.

Two End-of-Life (EoL) treatment processes were examined for CNFs, namely landfilling and recycling, and the results are shown in SI (Section S3, Fig. S4). Given that the final envisioned CNF-containing product in this study is a metal nano-catalyst supported on CNFs, an incineration process was considered for recycling, which would allow to retrieve the precious metal catalyst. While it is possible that different environmental impacts result from the EoL treatment of the two CNF alternatives (i.e., HNO₃- and HCl-treated CNFs), related to, for example, the O-groups present on the surface of the former, no data was available to model these differences with openLCA. Therefore, the calculated impacts are directly proportional to the mass of CNFs undergoing treatment, making HNO₃-treated CNFs more sustainable in terms of EoL treatment due to the definition of the reference flow. As can be observed in Fig. S4, landfilling has a higher environmental impact in most impact categories compared to incineration. However, the limitations of this conclusion should be raised, as the processes under comparison here do not consider the additional impacts of the metal nano-catalyst during landfilling, or the environmental benefits of reclaiming the metal nano-catalyst upon incineration. Taking into account the benefits of recycling the metal nano-catalyst would undoubtedly decrease the impact of the incineration process in all impact categories, as it would be credited with an avoided process (i.e., the process of producing the metal nano-catalyst from raw materials). Nevertheless, since it is not known which metal nano-catalyst would be supported on the CNFs under comparison here, these additional impacts and credits cannot be modelled. Practitioners are advised to properly account for these additional effects on a case-by-case basis when performing LCA.

Overall, the results shown in this section confirm the suitability of both open access tools used here to estimate the environmental impacts of NNMs along their lifecycle, and to help practitioners decide between process alternatives. Furthermore, both tools can be considered suitable to apply during Step A4 of SSbD assessment on NNMs, as they allow the calculation of characterization factors and quantification of environmental impacts along the lifecycle in both case studies, which could be further converted to absolute sustainability assessment results, as proposed by the SSbD framework [18,20], for example by applying a normalization method to the results. The applicability of USES-LCA for the assessment of human health and environmental impacts during the use phase of the NNMs (i.e., Step A3 of SSbD) was not evaluated here, as no information was available on the use phase of NNMs in the two case studies (i.e., type of surface and conditions of exposure for metal NNPs, type of metal-catalyzed reaction and corresponding conditions for CNF). SSbD practitioners are advised to investigate the applicability of this tool for Step A3 SSbD assessment on a case-by-case basis.

While the merit of both tools is evident for LCA and characterization factor calculation, neither tool was suitable to investigate nano-specific

impacts of NNMs. A detailed overview of suitable tools to predict NNM ecotoxicity is outside the scope of this work. Practitioners are advised to perform their own research on a case-by-case basis, to select suitable tools for nano-specific impact prediction, or previously published ecotoxicity results for NNMs with similar properties as the ones under investigation. Finally, considering the widespread utilization of LCA methodology, and the ubiquitous applicability of existing LCA libraries and impact assessment methods in multiple LCA tools, it would be advisable, for the development of novel toxicity prediction metrics and tools, to be compatible with existing LCA tools, by, for example, expressing toxicity in terms of equivalents using compounds that already exist in LCA libraries, in order to facilitate their integration in LCA tools by the practitioners.

3.4. Integrated assessment of NNMs with LICARA nanoscan tool

The LICARA nanoscan tool aims to help guide NNM developers through their decision-making processes about new nanoproducts. The tool serves to perform a comparative assessment between a novel nanoproduct and a conventional product with the same function. In order to use this tool, practitioners need to select a specific conventional material with equivalent functionality as the NNM under development, and to compare the two materials in terms of sustainability (e.g., amount of waste generated), performance for the selected functionality, risk, economic and social factors. The input parameters for each of the four NNMs examined are shown in SI (Section S4, Table S5), and the results of the assessment are shown in SI (Section S4, Fig.s S5 – S6).

In this study, the function of CNFs is to serve as support material for metal nano-catalysts. AC was selected as the conventional material, in order to perform the comparative analysis with the LICARA nanoscan tool. A comparative experimental evaluation of the specific CNFs described here with AC catalyst supports was not available, and therefore the experimental results of Gallegos-Suarez and co-workers [82] were used, who compared the catalytic activity of Ruthenium nano-catalyst supported on AC and carbon nanotubes for the hydrogenolysis of glycerol. For the purposes of this comparison, it was assumed that HNO₃-washed CNFs as catalyst support result in the same performance as carbon nanotubes described by the authors, and that the catalytic activity is directly proportional to the metal surface area, in order to estimate the catalytic activity of HCl-washed CNFs. Based on these assumptions, the activity for HNO₃-washed CNF and AC would equal 80 and 29 mmol substrate converted per gram metal per hour (as reported), whereas for HCl-washed CNFs it would equal to 22.4 mmol substrate converted per gram metal per hour. The reaction selectivity was also different between carbon nanotubes and AC in the experimental study, but since there is no clear way to predict the selectivity for the HCl-washed CNFs described here, this factor was not considered in the comparison. While catalyst deactivation was not discussed, it was assumed that HNO₃-washed CNF are less prone to deactivation than AC, given the higher catalytic activity reported for carbon nanotubes compared to AC after 24 hours [82]. For HCl-washed CNF, it was assumed that deactivation proceeds at the same rate as for AC-supported catalyst. To compare the two products in terms of sustainability, the environmental impacts of AC were considered as reported by Tiegam and co-workers [83], and compared to the results of the LCA analysis for CNFs performed here (Fig. 9).

It should be noted that for an accurate prediction of the comparative performance of novel NNMs and conventional reference products, practitioners should carefully select the sources of information, in order to reflect as precisely as possible the products under investigation, including, for example, the type of AC, and the envisioned type of catalytic conversion. Furthermore, the selection of a certain functionality and a corresponding reference material for comparison should be performed by the practitioners on a case-by-case basis. For example, besides their function as catalyst supports, carbonaceous materials can also be used as supercapacitors [84], adsorbents for various types of

contaminants [85–87] or for selective adsorption of gases [88], and their comparative assessment with the LICARA nanoscan tool may therefore result in different outcomes depending on the defined use case. In fact, the applicability of RA and LCA tools would be greatly enhanced if researchers developing novel NNMs would consistently report some possible “functionally equivalent” conventional materials already during the R&D stage, as this would allow more streamlined and unified evaluation of novel NNMs, and help guide scientific effort from an SSbD perspective at early stages of R&D.

For the case of metal NNPs with antimicrobial activity for surface coating, the hypothetical use case of a cylindrical door handle was assumed here, to allow the selection of a reference material for the comparison. The door handle is assumed to consist of stainless steel, with a radius of 5 cm and a thickness of 2 cm. The conventional product is considered to be coated with a homogeneous layer of metallic copper with a thickness of 1 mm, whereas the NNP-decorated product is considered to be coated with 4 grams of Cu NNPs or 1 gram of Ag NNPs. The antimicrobial activity is considered to be directly proportional to the surface area of the metal, which corresponds to approximately 220 cm² for the conventional product, 35.75 m² for 1 gram of Ag NNPs, and 116 m² for 4 grams of Cu NNPs (based on the specific surface area of the two metal NNP types shown in Table S1).

In agreement with the results of the LCA analysis (Fig. 10), Cu NNPs have higher environmental benefits from the manufacturing phase, compared to Ag NNPs, as predicted with the LICARA nanoscan tool (Fig. S5). On the contrary, and in agreement with the RA results (Figs. 5, 6, Table S3), Cu NNPs have higher risk, compared to Ag NNPs, considering the manufacturing phase and the integration of metal NNPs in the product (i.e., surface with antimicrobial coating) (Fig. S5). While the conflicting results between RA and LCA prevent the practitioner from making a clear decision between the two alternative metal NNPs for the envisioned use case, they provide guidance for mitigation measures that can be applied to decrease either the risk or environmental impact, by, for example, introducing risk management measures during the manufacturing stage to decrease the risk towards practitioners, or selecting different starting materials and/or manufacturing processes, which may result in lower environmental impact. Furthermore, environmental impact mitigation measures can also be considered in the manufacturing process, such as implementing systems for the capture and valorization or recirculation of exhaust gas. Importantly, NNPs that nucleate in the electric discharge reactor (Fig. 3) can be collected and processed into a new anode material, which can be reused in the synthesis process [66]. While sufficient information could not be retrieved in order to model this process in the LCA performed here, such measures should be considered by the practitioners, especially in cases where conflicting results between RA and LCA prevent a clear decision between process alternatives, as this may give a more clear advantage to one of the two NNP alternatives. Similarly, the EoL treatment of Ag and Cu NNPs, and particularly the possibility to recycle and re-use the two metals for the synthesis of NNPs, ought to be more carefully investigated and compared in terms of efficiency between the two metal alternatives, as this may significantly change the outcomes of the LCA along the life cycle of the two products, and more specifically the resource depletion potential of the two product alternatives. It should be noted that the societal and economic benefits between Ag and Cu NNPs were estimated to be the same with the LICARA nanoscan tool, given that both metal alternatives were evaluated to be similarly “better” or “worse” than the conventional material used in the analysis (i.e., bulk copper). Nevertheless, in this case, where conflicting results are achieved with RA and LCA methodology, one approach to help practitioners decide between process alternatives would be to perform a more detailed cost and/or social impact analysis, as this may result in a clear benefit for one of the two alternatives.

In the case of CNFs, both HNO₃- and HCl-treated CNFs have negative environmental benefits (i.e., higher environmental impacts) compared to AC, particularly due to the long duration of CVD and the utilization of

large volumes of hazardous carbon monoxide in this process. Nevertheless, significant benefits can be observed for HNO₃-treated CNFs compared to AC during the use and EoL phase, whereas this is not the case for HCl-treated CNFs (Fig. S6). In terms of RA, HNO₃-treated CNFs result in a clearly better score compared to HCl-treated CNFs, as was determined by the individual RA tools (Figs. 7, 8, Table S3), and the integrated assessment with the LICARA nanoscan tool (Fig. S6). Taken together, the results of LCA (Fig. 9), RA and integrated assessment all reveal the better performance of HNO₃-treated CNFs, compared to HCl-treated CNFs. Of course, as was also discussed throughout Section 3, a more careful definition of the functional unit should be performed by the practitioners, in terms of the potential disintegration of CNFs treated in concentrated HNO₃, as well as the exact reaction to be catalyzed by the CNF-supported catalyst under investigation, considering, for example, the interaction between the O-group-containing CNF surface with the reaction medium, substrate to be converted, product intermediate(s) and final product(s). Furthermore, the optimal metal nano-catalyst size and resulting catalytically-active metal surface area for the particular reaction should also be considered on a case-by-case basis when defining the functional unit of catalyst supports with different amounts of O-groups, compared to the rather simplistic definition adopted in the present study (i.e., the smaller the nano-catalyst’s size, the better). Practitioners should especially consider the specific catalytic reaction under investigation (e.g., in terms of temperature and components in the reaction medium), taking into account different mechanism of catalyst deactivation over time, wherein strong binding of the metal to the support’s O-groups may prevent deactivation via sintering at high temperatures [89], whereas small nanoparticles resulting from high concentration of O-groups may be more prone to deactivation via metal surface oxidation [90].

Overall, the results achieved with the integrated tool for the first use case (i.e., CNF as catalyst support) were in agreement with the results achieved using the individual RA tools (Sections 3.1 and 3.2), resulting in higher hazard and risk scores for HCl-washed CNF, compared to HNO₃-washed CNF. In terms of environmental sustainability, HNO₃-washed CNFs have lower environmental impacts compared to HCl-washed CNFs, as was also determined from the individual sustainability assessment tool (Section 3.3). Similarly, for the second use case (i.e., metal NNPs for antimicrobial coatings), the RA outcomes from the integrated tool were in agreement with the outcomes from the individual tools, which revealed lower Hazard and Risk scores for Ag NNP, compared to Cu NNP (Section 3.1 and 3.2). Furthermore, the environmental sustainability as estimated with the integrated tool was higher for Cu NNP, compared to Ag NNP, as was also the case with the individual tools (i.e., Section 3.3), with the exception of the metal NNP landfilling scenario (Fig. S3a), for which Cu NNPs had higher impacts due to the definition of the reference flow. While a wider investigation on the applicability of the LICARA nanoSCAN tool in other use cases would be required, the findings presented in this work indicate that it may be a suitable tool to provide a first screening and decision support among alternatives at early stages of NNM development, as a preliminary step before a full SSbD assessment.

4. Conclusions

In this study, different Environmental Impact Assessment / Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) tools (openLCA, USES-LCA), Risk Assessment (RA) tools (NanoSafer, Stoffenmanager Nano), and Integrated Assessment (LICARA nanoscan) tools were applied to perform the assessment of sustainability and risks for nanomaterials (NNMs), focusing on two case studies: carbon nanofibers (CNFs, as metal catalyst support materials) and metal nanoparticles (NNPs, as antimicrobial coatings on surfaces). These tools were selected on the basis of accessibility, with focus on open-access tools, ease of use, with focus on tools that do not require specialized knowledge by the practitioners, and suitability to help guide practitioners in selecting between alternatives (i.e., between different

compositions or different protocols for the manufacture of NNMs in each use case).

All the tools tested were able to distinguish between the two alternatives investigated in each use case (i.e., different elemental composition of metal NNPs, and different acids used for the preparation of CNFs). In the case of CNFs, a clear conclusion can be drawn with all the tools tested, wherein treatment of the NNMs with nitric acid resulted in higher sustainability and lower risks, compared to treatment with hydrochloric acid. On the contrary, in the case of metal NNPs, conflicting results were acquired by different tools, wherein Cu resulted in improved sustainability but higher risks, compared to Ag NNPs. In case of conflicting results, practitioners are advised to consider additional criteria, such as the economic and social aspects included in the integrated LICARA nanoscan tool, to investigate the entire lifecycle of products (including End-of-Life treatment), and to carefully evaluate adaptations to the manufacturing protocols, such as re-using materials in the synthesis of metal NNPs, which may help identify a more promising alternative between the ones examined. These recommendations further highlight the importance of the Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) framework in material development, which incorporates a full life cycle assessment of not only environmental, but also economic and social impacts, as well as the iterative application of a (Re-)Design phase and assessment phase, wherein material developers are expected to use the outcomes of the assessment to propose adaptations to the manufacturing process, in order to improve the overall SSbD score.

All individual assessment tools tested in the present manuscript were considered suitable for application in SSbD assessment, focusing on NNMs, as they allowed the quantification of several metrics relevant to the different steps of the SSbD assessment, as well as setting criteria and scoring of alternative materials. The only exception was the application of USES-LCA tool in hazard and exposure assessment during the use phase as part of Step A3 of SSbD, which was the original objective when selecting this tool. This could not be performed due to lack of information for the use phase of the selected case studies. Nevertheless, it is reasonably anticipated that material developers applying SSbD assessment during Research and Development (R&D) would have access to this information, and therefore it is advisable to test the suitability of USES-LCA on a case-by-case basis. Finally, it was shown that the simple, integrated NNM assessment tool tested (LICARA nanoSCAN) resulted in similar insights as the more specialized, individual assessment tools, for both RA and LCA and for both case studies. Therefore, a preliminary conclusion is that LICARA nanoSCAN can be used for pre-screening of NNMs, for example to select between process alternatives, especially at early stages of development, wherein time and data availability do not allow a complete SSbD assessment.

The results of different tools highlighted the importance of selecting a suitable functional unit for the assessment, which properly reflects the effectivity and lifetime of different material alternatives for a specific application, instead of comparing them on an equal mass basis. While the definition of a functional unit and corresponding reference flow as a basis for comparison is a mandatory part of LCA, it is not typically considered in comparative RA studies. Ideally, such functionality considerations, as well as functionally equivalent materials for comparison, can be identified and reported at early stages during NNM development, as this would facilitate the application of the SSbD approach during R&D.

It is important to note that the present work relies on hypothetical case studies, with data retrieved from literature, aiming to demonstrate the applicability of the selected tools. Therefore, more case studies on the application of RA and LCA tools in the context of SSbD assessment, as well as integrated tools, are needed, ideally using primary data from the R&D of NNMs, to further advance the application of SSbD in the field of NNMs. Furthermore, additional work is needed to incorporate NNM-specific knowledge into the toolbox of SSbD. For example, while the sustainability assessment performed here was suitable to investigate the entire lifecycle of NNMs, it was highlighted that neither of the tools

could predict nano-specific environmental impacts. Practitioners are advised to select ecotoxicity indicators on a case-by-case basis, as multiple tools and databases exist for different NNMs. To that end, future work could contribute to testing the applicability of existing, NNM-specific tools and databases for SSbD assessment. Finally, it would be advisable that developers of novel ecotoxicity prediction models take into account the existing tools for LCA, so that new databases and ecotoxicity results can be easy to combine and implement, by using a unified categorization and programming language, thus facilitating the integration into existing software.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Konstantina-Roxani Chatzipanagiotou: Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Visualization. **Foteini Petrakli:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Resources, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Joséphine Steck:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Investigation, Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Cécile Philippot:** Conceptualization, Validation, Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Sébastien Artous:** Conceptualization, Validation, Resources, Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Elias P. Koumoulos:** Conceptualization, Validation, Resources, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

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Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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